

...(in introduction)...

Effectively gauging performance and identifying sources of error has been a long-standing challenge in quantum computing, leaving the consideration of performance studies of algorithms like quantum arithmetic fairly limited beyond its theoretical discussion [1]. However, since the increase in access to NISQ hardware around 2018 and the subsequent boom in interest that accompanied it, great strides in the study of quantum noise and error correction have opened new paths for studying performance of quantum arithmetic. Ref. [3] provides performance results of quantum addition of up to 2-bit integers on the IBM Quantum superconducting-qubit testbed. While not specific to arithmetic, Ref. [2] examines the impact of various factors affecting a gate-based algorithm, including state preparation, oracle, connectivity, circuit rewriting, transpiling, and readout, and designed a calibration matrix to quantitatively evaluate the quantum error.

Despite these advances, a nuanced understanding of errors in quantum arithmetic and its implementation remains muddled by the complex nature of the quantum noise and small number of physical qubits available. In this work, we utilize the recent development and availability of tunable noise models to examine the impact of isolated sources of noise in quantum arithmetic. We limit the present study to the effects of 1q-gate and 2q-gate error rates, though model results for other isolated sources of error will be considered in a future work. In addition, we examine the impact of the AQFT on performance at different approximation depths, and its interaction with the aforementioned error rates. As the primary advantage of quantum arithmetic over classical arithmetic is the allowance of entangled states, we also perform novel calculations at varying degrees of superposition in the operands.

...(in results discussion)...

Like the 2-bit results of quantum addition seen in Ref. [3], with sufficiently high gate error rates we consistently observe results in an accuracy around 0%, as the length of the circuit and poor gate fidelity create too much noise to extract the solution without error mitigation and/or a more advanced success metric.

-
- [1] Amlan Chakrabarti and Susmita Sur-Kolay. Designing quantum adder circuits and evaluating their error performance. In *2008 International Conference on Electronic Design*, pages 1–6, 2008.
 - [2] Frank Leymann and Johanna Barzen. The bitter truth about gate-based quantum algorithms in the NISQ era. *Quantum Science and Technology*, 5(4):044007, sep 2020.
 - [3] Wiphoo Methachawalit and Prabhas Chongstitvatana. Adder circuit on ibm universal quantum comput-

ers. In *2020 17th International Conference on Electrical Engineering/Electronics, Computer, Telecommunications and Information Technology (ECTI-CON)*, pages 92–95, 2020.